

**Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with
Intersectional, Innovative, and Inclusive
Gender Equality Plans**

D3.1 SUPPORTER Capacity Building Scheme

European Science Foundation

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Submission date: [25. 01. 24]

- **GepSupporterProject**
- **company/gep-supporter-project/**
- **@GEP_SUPPORTER**
- **Supporterproject**

Project acronym: SUPPORTER

Project title: SecUring sPORTs Education thRough innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans

Grant agreement number: 101094529

Start date of project: [01. 04. 23]

Deliverable title: SUPPORTER capacity building scheme

Due date of deliverable: [30. 11. 23]

Actual date of submission: [25. 01. 24]

File name: SUPPORTER_D3.1_SUPPORTER capacity building scheme.docx

Organisation Responsible for Deliverable: European Science Foundation (ESF)

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Status: Final

Dissemination Level: PU

Work Package: 3

Keywords: Gender Equality, capacity building; mutual learning

Please cite as:

Vilarchao, E., Ververidou, F., Tatsioka, Z., Lundvall, S., Zaharis, N., Strid, S., & Ipolyi, I. (2024). D3.1. SUPPORTER Capacity Building Scheme. 61 pages.

Revision history

Version	Date	Revised by	Comments
01	24/11/2023	Eugenia Vilarchao & Ildiko Ipolyi (ESF)	First draft shared with core team
02	05/12/2023	UGOT, SEERC	Contributions to sections 2-4
03	05/01/2024	UGOT, SEERC, ESF	Second round of feedback to sections 2-4
04	15/01/2024	Eugenia Vilarchao & Ildiko Ipolyi (ESF)	Feedback integrated, document shared with consortium and reviewers
05	19/01/2024	All consortium	Feedback sent to authors
06	25/01/2024	Eugenia Vilarchao & Ildiko Ipolyi (ESF)	Feedback integrated; deliverable submitted to EC

Acknowledgement

This project is funded by the European Union

Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
IOs	Implementing Organisations
M&M	Mentoring and Monitoring Meetings
WPLs	Work Package Leaders
4I-GEPs	Innovative, Intersectional, Inclusive and Impactful Gender Equality Plans

The SUPPORTER project

SUPPORTER, “SecUring sPORTs Education thRough innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans”, is an EU-funded project running from April 2023 until September 2025. Launched on 19. April 2023, it aims to support eight sports higher education institutions from Central and Eastern Europe in developing their own intersectional, innovative, inclusive and impactful Gender Equality Plans which explicitly address gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

Through mutual learning and interactive exchanges, the project will seek to:

1. Identify and document systemic challenges faced by sports higher education institutions in advancing gender equality and eradicating gender-based violence.
2. Develop activities tailored to each partner institution.
3. Strengthen the sports institutions’ organisational capacity to address gender equality with an intersectional approach.
4. Foster an inclusive institutional culture by developing mutual-learning processes.
5. Strengthen networking and exchange among sports institutions and with communities of practice.
6. Foster gender-related institutional, sustainable, transformative changes in the sports institutions with a specific attention on the challenge of gender-based violence -thus ultimately fostering the institutions and their Gender Equality Plans’ inclusiveness and the overall adherence to intersectionality.

While initially partnering with eight institutions, the SUPPORTER project aspires to target and reach the wider sports ecosystem and its various organisations in Central and Eastern Europe and beyond, and in the long run contribute to wide societal changes.

Project Partners

	European Science Foundation (ESF)
	Göteborgs Universitet (UGOT), Sweden
	Kentro Erevnon Notioanatolikis Evropis Astiki mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia, The South-East European Research Centre (SEERC), Greece
	Univerzitet u Banjoj Luci (UNIBL), Bosnia & Herzegovina
	Univerza v Ljubljani (UL), Slovenia
	Univerzita Karlova (CU), Czechia
	Natsionalna Sportna Akademiya Vassil Levski (NSA), Bulgaria
	Lietuvos Sporto Universitetas (LSU), Lithuania
	Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara (UVT), Romania
	Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport (GSTUPES), Georgia
	Universitatea de Stat de Educație Fizică și Sport (USEFS), Moldova

Summary

This deliverable outlines the capacity building scheme of the SUPPORTER project, a dynamic and comprehensive program strategically designed to equip Implementing Organisations (IOs) within sports institutions in Central and Eastern Europe with essential knowledge and skills to advance gender+ equality in-house and in their networks.

The deliverable describes the interconnection of the three-core capacity-building project activities: the Training Scheme, the Mutual Learning Scheme, and the Mentoring and Monitoring Scheme, and explains how they function in a synergistic manner, providing guidance, promoting an efficient knowledge exchange, and creating sustainable impact.

The training scheme equips the IOs with the necessary knowledge to develop and start implementing their institutional roadmaps towards gender+ equality and innovative, intersectional, inclusive and impactful Gender Equality Plans (4I-GEP). The Mutual Learning Scheme encourages peer-to-peer exchange, fostering collaboration and sharing best practices among participants, while the Mentoring and Monitoring Scheme provides ongoing support and feedback.

These elements work intertwined, building on each other's input and output, and ensuring a sustainable learning process and implementation of the institutional roadmaps for the IOs. The interplay between these core activities is fully described in this deliverable together with a detailed description of each of these activities (Sections 2-4).

Highlights

- The capacity building scheme is built on a well-structured **methodological plan** comprising three core interlinked project activities: training, mutual learning, and mentoring and monitoring.
- The capacity building plan's **key characteristics are adaptability and interconnection**.
- The **comprehensive training program**, with three thematic modules and overall, nine training sessions, covers a wide spectrum of gender+ equality topics, from fundamental concepts to more complex issues like addressing systemic and organisational gender-based violence.
- The **mutual learning scheme includes a multi-layered organisational learning process** which goes beyond traditional training by the organisation of consortium-wide mutual learning workshops, periodic mutual learning sessions addressing particularly relevant topics and bilateral mutual learning meetings.
- The development and implementation of the roadmaps will be followed by **periodic mentoring and monitoring activities**.

Introduction

The SUPPORTER capacity-building is a comprehensive dynamic scheme designed to empower Implementing Organisations (IOs) in Central and Eastern European sports institutions (universities/faculties) with the essential knowledge and skills for advancing gender+ equality. The scheme is core to the SUPPORTER methodology.

The SUPPORTER methodology unfolds through three interconnected and complementary processes. First, the **analytical process** involved mapping activities, providing profound insights crucial for driving the project's implementation. This encompassed mapping the theoretical background (Strid et al., 2023), as well as identifying available training tools and materials (Grahn et al., 2023).

Subsequently, the reflective and implementation processes run in two strongly interconnected strands: one run by the IOs and, the other one run by the core team composed of the work package leaders (WPLs).

Within the **reflective process**, the strand of the IOs has started with a reflective self-assessment exercise (further detailed in Section 1.4.3) and continues throughout the roadmap co-creation and implementation. This process is enriched by mutual learning workshops and mentoring and monitoring events facilitating periodic examinations of the progress and allowing the integration of evaluation steps into the design of their institutional roadmaps. This approach empowers the IOs to engage in a continuous self-evaluation throughout the entire project.

Simultaneously, the core team's reflective strand started with WP3 “Horizontal capacity-building” and the current deliverable, involving the formulation of training and mutual learning (ML) schemes. These schemes will continuously adapt to the needs of the IOs throughout the roadmap co-creation and implementation - and will be similarly enriched by the mentoring and monitoring meetings (M&Ms).

The **implementation process** focuses on co-design and implementation of the institutional roadmaps with the goal of developing 4I-GEPs and fostering inclusive gender+ equality. Additionally, it aims to generate a wide range of outputs, including a compilation of lessons learned, SUPPORTER guidelines and recommendations, and policy briefs. This process is further informed and refined through the feedback collected from the broader reflective process.

The current deliverable focuses mainly on the work undertaken by the core team strand throughout the reflective and implementation processes.

1. Capacity building scheme

SUPPORTER's capacity-building scheme describes the strategy that will be undertaken throughout the project in order to ensure that the IOs acquire the essential knowledge and skills for advancing gender+ equality at their institutions. This strategy considers the diverse institutional contexts, the existing institutional GEPs, and the varying levels of knowledge on gender equality among the IOs.

The capacity building scheme follows three main principles: adaptability and flexibility, continuous assessment and feedback, and anticipation. The first one underscores that **the scheme is not a rigid plan but an evolving pathway** that can be in continuous process of adaptation according to the needs and obstacles found during the different project activities. The second involves gathering information at every step of the project to assess the current activities and provide feedback for the planning of the next cycle of activities. Anticipation, the third principle, involves planning activities based on the needs assessment conducted explicitly (e.g. asking the IOs which trainings they need) or implicitly inferring from the outcomes of project activities (e.g. inferring from their institutional mappings where are the knowledge gaps).

1.1 Design

The capacity building scheme is composed of three core activity lines of the project: **training, mutual learning, and mentoring and monitoring**. These core activities are interlinked and follow the aforementioned three principles in order to provide tailored capacity building to the IOs, and ultimately ensure the effective implementation of the roadmaps (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Capacity building scheme cycle

The horizontal capacity building scheme draws upon the results of three mapping activities conducted in WP2 during the analytical phase (see Section 1.4. Mapping activities). These activities encompassed: 1. Mapping of the state of the art of gender+ equality and gender-based violence policies in the context of sport education and the IOs; 2. The mapping of existing trainings that address gender equality and gender-based violence developed by other EU-funded projects

and other initiatives; and 3. The mapping of the IOs institutional settings including an analysis of their current organisational GEP.

While the mapping activities described above primarily generate theoretical awareness among IOs about the addressed challenges, the training scheme is designed to furnish them with practical knowledge and skills essential for undertaking activities to assure institutional changes towards gender+ equality.

In this view, the SUPPORTER capacity-building scheme delivers a comprehensive three-module training scheme, consisting of nine sessions (see Section 3 Training scheme). It spans over a diverse array of gender+ equality topics, commencing with fundamental subjects such as gender and gender equality within the EU framework and progressively advancing to more intricate areas such as systemic and organisational gender-based violence.

In order to trigger the in-depth engagement of the IOs, to ensure that the transferred knowledge consolidates, but also to foster knowledge exchange among the IOs, each completed training module is followed by the organisation of an in-person mutual learning workshops - in total three. Additionally, five online mutual learning sessions complement the capacity building scheme and promote regular and meaningful interaction among the IOs throughout the different stages of the project.

The mentoring and monitoring scheme will support the co-design and implementation of institutional roadmaps, fostering self-reflection and providing the IOs with tailored feedback, resources and strategic guidance. Eight M&Ms are scheduled on a regular basis along the project between each IO and the SUPPORTER core team.

1.2 Strategic learning topics

In order to ensure that the IOs acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to develop and implement their 4I-GEPs, the capacity-building thematic approach span over the topics that need to be addressed for each of the recommended six steps of the development of a GEP ([EIGE's GEAR tool](#)). These are:

- 1) Getting started: Getting inspiration.
- 2) Gender Analysis: Analysing and assessing the status of gender equality in the organisation.
- 3) Setting up the GEP: Identification of objectives, setting targets and measures to remedy the identified problems, allocating resources and responsibilities, and defining timelines.
- 4) Implementation: Implementing the planned activities and enlarging the stakeholders' network.
- 5) Monitoring & evaluation: Assessment of the implementation process and the progress achieved against the aims and objectives identified in the GEP.
- 6) What next?: Development of the next GEP building on experiences, learnings and achievements, while ensuring the sustainability of these actions.

Figure 2 – GEP design cycle

The first step is covered by Training Module 1 and its corresponding mutual learning workshop (September 2023) and mutual learning sessions (December 2023 – March 2024). The second and third step will be covered by Training Module 2 (April – May 2024) and its corresponding mutual learning workshop and sessions (June 2024; September – December 2024). Finally, the fourth, fifth and sixth steps will be covered at the final year of the project by Training Module 3 (January – February 2025) and its respective mutual learning activities (March – June 2025).

1.3 Overall timeline

Figure 3 – Capacity building scheme timeline.

TM= Training Module; MLW= Mutual Learning Workshop; ▲= Mutual Learning Sessions; M&M= Mentoring and Monitoring meetings.

1.4 Mapping activities

As part of the analytical phase of the project three mapping exercises were conducted. First, the mapping of gender+ equality and gender-based violence policies (section 1.4.1); second, the mapping of available trainings and training resources from current or previous EC-funded projects with a specific focus on trainings on structural changes and GEP as a tool for it, gender-based violence, and gender+ equality in sport (section 1.4.2). Lastly, the IOs were asked to conduct an institutional mapping and self-assessment of their existing GEP (section 1.4.3).

1.4.1 Mapping the state of the art of gender+ equality and gender-based violence in the context of sports education and research

A thorough examination of the state-of-the-art in gender+ equality and gender-based violence within sports education institutions, focusing on the unique contexts of the IOs was conducted over the first four months of the project under Task 2.1 and its results are described in the [D2.1 “Inclusive gender+ equality policy and practice in sport higher education institutions”](#) (Strid et al. 2023). This work established the theoretical foundation of the SUPPORTER project, elucidating the baseline gender equality and gender-based violence policies in the context of the IOs, and providing a comprehensive literature review, the identification of key issues, proposed solutions, mapping of IOs' policy implementation, and a set of recommendations based on theoretical frameworks and best practices.

Key points emerging from D2.1 stress the imperative for gender equality policies in sports education to emphasise courses promoting equality and social justice, addressing discrimination on various grounds. The identification and support of internal change agents are highlighted, emphasising the commitment of leadership to gender equality. The document also emphasises the need for robust action plans to prevent, protect, and prosecute gender-based violence, aligning with existing legislations. Moreover, it underscores the importance of assessing organisational capacities, linking and jointly monitoring gender policies, and addressing intersectionality issues in sports education. Importantly, the literature review identifies a literature gap specific to the Central and Eastern European context, reinforcing the critical relevance of SUPPORTER's focus in this region.

These key points feed into the development of subsequent training sessions and mutual learning activities.

1.4.2 Mapping of available training material, tools and trainers

Available trainings and resources coming from present and past EC-funded projects on gender equality and structural change were compiled in [D2.2 “Training materials and tools for institutional transformation”](#) (Grahm et al., 2023). This deliverable serves as a comprehensive mapping and evaluation of existing training materials and tools within EC-funded projects, emphasising systemic institutional transformation for gender equality and a specific focus on gender-based violence. It provides an overview of available resources, acting as an inspiration for the development of the SUPPORTER training scheme. The document assesses existing trainings and tools against pre-defined criteria for their applicability in the context of SUPPORTER's IOs and provides

recommendations for the design and implementation of the training scheme. It is complemented by a list of experienced trainers on gender equality, gender+ equality and intersectionality in relation to GEPs and higher education institutions.

The deliverable highlights the abundance of online trainings for GEPs but notes the peripheral treatment of gender-based violence. It underscores the importance of active participation, mutual learning, and community practices, identifies a lack of sport-focused higher education trainings, the absence of an intersectionality perspective, and the need for leadership representation within the target audience. This mapping and analysis served for the development of the training scheme (see Section 2).

1.4.3 Self-Assessment for the Implementing Organisations

A self-assessment template (see Annex 1) was prepared for the SUPPORTER IOs to guide them on the reflection on their institutional settings regarding gender equality with three main aims:

1. Analysing their existing institutional GEP, reflecting on the scope and targets, identifying strengths and gaps in relationship to the EC recommended areas, and analysing the 41 dimensions of their current GEP.
2. Describing the institutional baseline at the beginning of the project in order to assure a reference point for the assessment of the achieved institutional changes at the end of the project.
3. Reflecting and preparing for the next step in the roadmap development.

The self-assessment exercise is placed in the interphase of the analytical process and the reflective process of the SUPPORTER project. The analytical process includes the mapping of national and institutional policies (D2.1), done by the IOs with the support of UGOT. The reflective process begins with the self-assessment providing a detailed mapping of the institutional arrangements, opportunities and challenges that could then be used to co-create the roadmaps.

The template was presented to the IOs in bilateral meetings with the task leader (ESF). After its completion a second set of meetings were organised individually with each IO and the core members ESF and SEERC. During this second round there was a discussion around some unclear answers as well as a request for further information.

As the aim of the exercise was to have a realistic picture of the existing GEP and institutional arrangements, the results will be kept internal to the project, and the IOs were reassured that if at certain point some information will be publicly released, their consent will be requested in advance.

The results of this exercise were summarised internally in an excel file (containing the main answers of the self-assessment for all the IOs), and in a document listing the highlights together with a set of recommendations for the core team to be taken into account when designing the next steps (ML sessions/workshops, roadmap templates and training sessions).

The main highlights of this exercise were:

1. The general understanding of the mandatory elements of the GEP needs to be reinforced and support must be given to the IOs to include the mandatory and the recommended elements (specially addressing gender-based violence) in the SUPPORTER GEPs tailoring to the sports field.
2. The stakeholder mapping and strategy for engagement needs to be reinforced together with the concept of 'change agents' and the related 'working group' or 'core team'.
3. Some organisations showcased good examples that could serve for the other IOs therefore the next mutual learning sessions need to foster this transfer of knowledge.

4. Some of the IOs have trainings tackling certain aspects particular to gender equality in sports. The identification of possible trainers from the IOs to the IOs is considered under SUPPORTER training scheme.

1.5 The case of the ‘model GEP institution’

The aim of the ‘model GEP institution’ was to have within the SUPPORTER consortium a higher education sport institution or faculty that would serve as a ‘model’ in terms of advanced gender+ equality policies and GEPs to the participating IOs. This role was attributed to Göteborgs Universitet Faculty of Education, Department of Food and Nutrition and Sport Science (UGOT-Sport), whose qualities were described in SUPPORTER’s Grant Agreement (Part B – page 7) as follows:

“UGOT is an advanced gender equality institution with an overall, comprehensive, process and plan for gender+ equality work, and UGOT-Sport has its own local (department-specific) operational/implemented inclusive and intersectional action plan for its gender+ equality and equal opportunities work as well. Therefore, with the central and local (department-specific) GEPs, designed and implemented through systematic gender transformation work, UGOT-Sport is the SUPPORTER advanced gender equality institution and takes the specific role of model institution”.

However, when SUPPORTER started there was an agreement among the WPLs to nuance and contextualise the concept of ‘model institution’; what serves as a model in one context might not serve as a model in another context. As for the current definition, the ‘model institution’ serves as a forward-thinking institution that, despite its advanced progress in terms of gender+ equality, recognises the necessity for continuous improvement. Therefore, **the ‘model institution’ is not showcased as an example of ‘model’ policies and GEP actions to follow but rather as an example of progress, embodying a key feature of GEPs: ‘progression’**. It aims to demonstrate to the IOs that even in advanced institutions, there exists an ongoing need for systematic improvement. This perspective encourages a dynamic, critical and forward-looking approach to institutional transformation, fostering a culture of innovation and continuous improvement.

1.5.1 Activities

The ‘model institution’ participated in the self-assessment exercise completing the template in the same way as the IOs (Annex 1). The exercise helped to identify the main highlights of gender+ policies and actions in the GEP and the areas where improvement is needed. The results were presented to the IOs at a Mutual Learning Session held online on December 11, 2023. Examples of innovative measures were given with examples from recruitment processes, valuing of merits and qualifications, as well as examples of what is included under the concept gender-based violence (e.g. bodily integrity and gender-based vulnerabilities).

At each mutual learning activity (online sessions or workshop) the ‘model institution’ will have a slot in the agenda to present their activities, experiences and best practices related to the specific topic of the mutual learning activity. At each presentation emphasis on the needs for improvement will be made and possible activities will be discussed with the IOs.

2. Training scheme

The SUPPORTER training scheme aims to equip the IOs with the practical knowledge and skills necessary to pursue their institutional changes towards gender+ equality, using their GEPs as a means.

It delivers a three-module training to all participating IOs, comprised by nine training sessions covering a wide range of gender+ equality topics starting from the baseline including gender and gender equality in the EU framework, and gradually reaching more complex ones such as systemic and organisational gender-based violence.

The logic of the trainings follows the six main steps of a GEP (described in section 1.2), so that each module addresses the knowledge and practice needed to design and implement each step for a 4I-GEP and is based on the three SUPPORTER mapping activities (see section 1.4) and their products D2.1, D2.2 and the outcomes of T2.3.

With reference to the capacity building scheme being an evolving pathway, each module 2 and 3 also draws on the feedback from the previous trainings and mutual learning activities, the mentoring and monitoring meetings, and feeds into the subsequent mutual learning activities and training to ensure that the scheme meets the actual needs of the consortium IOs.

2.1 Format

The training scheme consists of three modules, each one comprising three half-day training sessions (totalling at nine), following a structured script. The format includes both offline and online trainings – 1 offline and 8 online.

Each one of the nine sessions – both offline and online - starts with a clear introduction and warm-up exercise, followed by the presentation of the theoretical element underpinning the focus of the session.

The presentation of the theoretical element is followed by practical group exercises on themes related to the topic. The group work among the IOs, where each group appoints a note taker and a rapporteur; is facilitated as needed by a core partner and the trainer does a round of the groups to support the exercise and help advance the discussion.

The results of the exercise and group work are shared in plenary by the group rapporteurs and discussed among the IOs to facilitate mutual learning.

Each session ends with a feedback questionnaire, the learning from which is used to improve the following training sessions.

Training sessions are delivered by in-consortium or invited external expert trainers.

As mentioned before, in order to consolidate the learnings of training modules, exchange related good practices, share questions and overall experiences, the completion of each training module is accompanied by the organisation of a mutual learning workshop and other mutual learning sessions.

During the M&Ms the core team together with the IOs assess the concrete application of the learnings into their roadmap design and implementation, and also the needs for further training on specific topics.

2.2 Topics

The training addresses the theory and practice, and knowledge and skills needed to set up and implement a 4I-GEP, and as previously described, structured to address each of the six main steps of a GEP (see section 1.2 and Figure 2).

The first module is a basic training on key concepts, institutional change, gender equality and GEPs, addressing the first step of a GEP: *Getting started, getting inspiration*.

The second module is an intermediate training on gender equality and inclusive and progressive GEPs, addressing the second and third steps of a GEP: *Analysing and assessing the status quo in the organisation, and Setting up a gender equality plan, identification of objectives, setting targets and measures to remedy the identified problems, allocating resources and responsibilities, and defining timelines. It will also further explore the 4Is and their operationalisation for the sport context*.

The third module is an advanced training on gender equality in sports higher education and research institutions, including 4I-GEPs, addressing the fourth, fifth and sixth step of a GEP: *Implementation: implementing the planned activities and enlarging the stakeholders' network, Monitoring & evaluation: assessment of the implementation process and the progress achieved against the aims and objectives identified in the GEP, and What next?: development of the next GEP building on experiences, learnings and achievements, while ensuring the sustainability of these actions*.

The next sections provide an overview of the Training Modules' content, for further details on the learning objectives of the module and the content of each session see Annex 2.

2.2.1 Training Module 1: Basic training on key concepts, institutional change, gender equality, gender-based violence and GEPs

This first of three modules is a basic training to ensure a shared understanding of key concepts and contexts. Over three sessions, it addresses:

- Key concepts, e.g., gender, gender+, intersectionality, gender-based violence
- Main issues at stake regarding gender equality in research and higher education in the context of sport
- Prevalence and consequences of gender-based violence in the European Research Area
- Policies on gender equality and gender-based violence in the European Research Area
- Gender equality plans as the main instrument towards institutional change. Introduction to the six steps of a gender equality plan.
- Learn about prerequisites and key success factors of institutional change processes.
- Gain awareness about how to facilitate change and how to deal with resistances.

This module is composed of the following sessions:

- Session 1: Key concepts and shared understanding.
- Session 2: Institutional change.
- Session 3: Gender equality plans.

2.2.2 Training Module 2: Intermediate training on gender equality and inclusive and progressive gender equality plans

The second module turns the focus to the sports environment and the specifics in the context of sport higher education and research. It addresses the second and third step of the gender equality plan, including analysing and assessing the state of play in the institution to provide insights on which measures need to be implemented, and setting up a 4I-GEP. It uses the impact drivers to support transformative aspects of the IOs gender equality plans, including core team of change agents, capacity/skills of the change agents for driving institutional change; leadership actively committed; availability of resources; data collection and statistical analysis; involvement of internal stakeholders, involvement of external stakeholders and experts; coverage of the different dimensions/areas of gender equality institutional change; transparency and accountability; institutional policy making based on a robust understanding of gender equality; organisational culture; and organisational governance.

This module is composed of the following sessions:

- Session 1: Analysis and assessment of the state-of-play in the institution: data collection and data analysis; focus on sport higher education institutions – focus data.
- Session 2: Analysis and assessment of the state-of-play in the institution: measures, policy and legislation; focus on sport higher education institutions – focus policy and measures.
- Session 3: Setting up a gender equality plan; focus on sport higher education institutions.

2.2.3 Training Module 3: Advanced training on gender+ equality and 4I-GEPs

This third and final module is an advanced training on gender+ equality and 4I-GEPs in the sports environment. It builds on the first two modules of trainings and mutual learning, and work carried out by the IOs T2.1 and T2.3. The focus of the training is the fourth, fifth and sixth steps of the gender equality plan, implementation, monitoring & evaluation, and what happens after the gender equality plan. Key concepts are reviewed. It revisits the overall meaning of intersectional, innovative, inclusive and impactful GEPs by discussing the theory and by providing examples from the 'model institution' and other organisations.

This module is composed of the following sessions:

- Session 1: Implementing a gender equality plan (step 4).
- Session 2: Monitoring progress and evaluating of a gender equality plan (step 5).

- Session 3: What comes after the gender equality plan (step 6).

2.3 Timeline

	Topic	Format	Planned date or month
Training Module 1			
Training Session 1	Key concepts and a shared understanding	Online	M9, September 2023
Training Session 2	Institutional change	Online	M9, September 2023
Training Session 3	Gender equality plans, six steps	Offline (Strasbourg)	M9, September 2023
Training Module 2			
Training Session 1	Analysis and assessment: data	Online	M13, April 2024
Training Session 2	Analysis and assessment: policy	Online	M13, April 2024
Training Session 3	Setting up a GEP	Online	M14, May 2024
Training Module 3			
Training Session 1	Implementation	Online	M21, January 2025
Training Session 2	Monitoring and evaluation	Online	M22, February 2025
Training Session 3	Post-GEP, what comes next?	Online	M22, February 2025

3. Mutual learning scheme

The mutual learning scheme comprises a set of systematic mutual learning activities taking place throughout the running of the capacity building scheme. The scheme aims at facilitating the consolidation of insights and experiences gained throughout the training programme, the co-design and implementation of the institutional roadmaps, as well as the exchange of ideas, challenges and experiences among the consortium IOs in an assisted environment.

3.1 Format

The mutual learning scheme consists of three 1.5-day mutual learning workshops, five half-day mutual learning sessions, and two bilateral mutual learning meetings among IOs. The three mutual learning workshops take place offline and follow the completion of each training module, while the five mutual learning sessions are offered online. Both activities are designed and delivered by the SUPPORTER core team, but also involve the active contribution and participation of IOs as they aim at fostering the exchange of good practices. The bilateral meetings among IOs also take place online.

3.2 Topics

The mutual learning workshops address topics elaborating on the knowledge acquired and ideas discussed during the training modules, while the mutual learning sessions topics are tailored to respond to specific needs and obstacles the IOs could run into when designing and implementing the roadmaps. The next sections provide an overview of the mutual learning workshops and mutual learning sessions content, for further details on the objectives and the content of each activity see Annex 3.

3.2.1 Mutual Learning Workshops

The three mutual learning workshops build upon the knowledge acquired through the training modules and provide IOs with the opportunity to engage in constructive dialogue, exchange best practices, experiences and ideas that will facilitate and contribute actively to the development of 4I-GEPs.

The workshops have the following objectives:

1. Enable knowledge transfer and consolidation of the information acquired during the training modules;
2. Prepare IOs for the institutional mapping, the co-design and implementation of the institutional roadmaps;
3. Foster reflections and discussions among IOs on best practices and lived experiences.

3.2.2 Mutual Learning Sessions

Five mutual learning sessions are organised periodically to address specific needs and obstacles IOs might face during the implementation of the roadmaps. The 'Model Institution' and its best practices will function as a basis for discussion and exchange of good practices during the various mutual learning sessions.

Objectives:

1. Inform IOs about the co-creation and implementation process and the key steps to be taken.
2. Offer guidance and support to IOs during the roadmap implementation phase by addressing challenges and obstacles.
3. Provide IOs with the opportunity to exchange ideas and reflect on good practices that will inform their 4I-GEPs and facilitate the roadmap implementation.
4. Contribute to the development of sustainable 4I-GEPs with a clear focus on sports education.

The Mutual Learning Sessions follow these topics:

- **Mutual learning session I:** Introduction to Roadmaps: Co-design.

- **Mutual learning session II:** Roadmap Implementation: Challenges and Engagement of Stakeholders.
- **Mutual learning session III:** Roadmap Implementation: Focus on Sports Education Institutions.
- **Mutual learning session IV:** Roadmap Implementation: gender-based Violence.
- **Mutual learning session V:** Roadmap Implementation: Sustainability and Long-Term Planning.

3.3.3 Bilateral Meetings

Two bilateral mutual learning meetings will take place among pairs of IOs during the roadmap's implementation period. Additional meetings may be scheduled on a needs-basis. The IOs will be paired based on the similarity of the roadmaps and their institutional context.

The bilateral meetings have the following objectives:

- Provide IOs with the opportunity to exchange experiences, strategies, and feedback on the implementation of their institutional roadmaps.
- Provide a safe environment where IOs can discuss potential challenges in the definition of the 4I-GEPs.

3.3 Timeline

	Topic	Format	Participation	Date
Mutual learning workshop I	Introduction to the Mutual learning programme Reflection on the first training module Introduction to the self-reflexive exercise	Offline (Strasbourg)	Consortium	M6, September 2023
Mutual learning session I	Introduction to Roadmaps: Co-design	Online	Consortium	M9, December 2023
Mutual learning session II	Roadmap implementation: Challenges and engagement of stakeholders	Online	Consortium	M12, March 2024
Mutual learning workshop II	Reflection on Training Module II: Gender+ segregated data and state/local policies and regulations	Offline (Thessaloniki)	Consortium	M15, June 2024
Mutual learning session III	Roadmap implementation: Focus on sports education institutions	Online	Consortium	M18, September 2024

Mutual learning session IV	Roadmap Implementation: Gender-based violence	Online	Consortium	M21, December 2024
Mutual learning workshop III	Reflection on Training Module III: GEP implementation, monitoring and evaluation	Offline (Ljubljana)	Consortium	M24, March 2025
Mutual learning session V	Roadmap Implementation: Sustainability and Long-term planning	Online	Consortium	M27, June 2025
Bilateral Meeting I	Roadmap implementation	Online	Among IOs	M14-M19, May 2024-October 2024
Bilateral Meeting II	Roadmap implementation	Online	Among IOs	M19-M24, October 2024-March 2025

4. Mentoring and monitoring scheme

The mentoring and monitoring scheme aims to oversee and guide the co-design and implementation phases of institutional roadmaps by IOs. Through a self-reflective process, SUPPORTER core team assists the IOs in the identification of good practices, the consolidation of learnings, the identification of needs for further trainings, facilitating the achievement of the roadmap's objectives and, ultimately, the development of the 4I-GEP. In other words, the monitoring activities ensure the impact assessment of the Grounding Actions, namely the concrete sets of activities which comprise each institutional roadmap and favour institutional change, while the mentoring activities are designed to enhance the effectiveness of the roadmap development and implementation, and to foster a long-term vision of the Grounding Actions with an eye on the post-project period and to promote sustainability of the outcomes and actions beyond the SUPPORTER project's lifespan.

4.1 Format

The induction to the mentoring and monitoring scheme took place during the first mutual learning workshop in Strasbourg in September 2023. Apart from this first meeting, the scheme consists of at least seven online meetings, held on a regular basis between each IO and the SUPPORTER core team. The IOs are responsible, with the support of the core team, to organise and carry out these meetings (including drafting the agenda and keeping the meeting minutes).

The main premise for M&Ms will be the learning diaries (Annex 4) developed by each IO. Resembling a field book, the learning diaries constitute a comprehensive record of all completed

activities or relevant reflections of the IO within a designated period. To inform the development of training activities tailored to the needs of the IOs, two learning diaries (1 and 5) are dedicated to collect reflections on previous training sessions and to identify the topics on which further training is required. The rest of the learning diaries (2, 3, 4, 6, and 7) are dedicated to report on the roadmap actions and overall project's activities and outcomes; these will be shared with the core team prior to the meetings. In the last two M&Ms, attention will be steered towards the sustainability of the Grounding Actions, the capitalisation of the learnings, and the development of the 4I-GEP.

4.2 Timeline

	Topic of discussion	Format	Planned date or month
M&M 1	Induction to the mentoring and monitoring scheme	Online	M6, 13-14 Sep 2023
M&M 2	Self-assessment exercise (T2.3)	Online	M8, Nov 2023
M&M 3	Co-design of roadmap	Online	M11, Feb 2024
M&M 4	Learning Diary 2 (Implementation of roadmap)	Online	M14, May 2024
M&M 5	Learning Diary 3 (Implementation of roadmap)	Online	M18, Sep 2024
M&M 6	Learning Diary 4 (Implementation of roadmap)	Online	M21, Dec 2024
M&M 7	Learning Diary 6 (Implementation of roadmap - Update of GEP into 4I-GEP)	Online	M25, Apr 2025
M&M 8	Learning Diary 7 (Implementation of roadmap – Update of GEP into 4I-GEP)	Online	M28, Jul 2025

Conclusions

SUPPORTER's capacity building scheme is more than a set of activities; it is a comprehensive transformative journey that strategically links three core project activities: the training scheme, the mutual learning scheme, and the mentoring and monitoring scheme, and provides the structural backbone to SUPPORTER.

These interconnected elements work in synergy, creating a robust ecosystem for capacity building that facilitates efficient knowledge exchange, provides guidance, and fosters a sustainable impact for the IOs. The capacity building scheme empowers the IOs to develop and implement roadmaps towards gender+ equality institutional changes, to ensure the sustainability of these changes, and to ultimately design 4I-GEPs adapted to the sports field.

A report of this transformative journey will be available at the end of the project (M30, September 2025): D3.2: "Report on the implementation of the capacity building scheme". This report will summarise the impact of the implementation of the training programme, the mutual learning scheme, and the mentoring and monitoring scheme, and will discuss the possible adaptations made to respond to the needs of the IOs.

References

EIGE (2016). *Roadmap to gender equality plans in research and higher education institutions. A short guide*. https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/gear_roadmap_01_shortguide.pdf

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Annex 1 – Self-Assessment template

**Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with
Intersectional, Innovative, and Inclusive
Gender Equality Plans**

Institutional self-assessment

[ACRONYM OF THE PARTNER]

Author

Submission date: [DD. MM. YY]

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INTRODUCTION

This document serves the SUPPORTER implementing organisations (IOs) (sport universities or sport faculties) to reflect on their institutional settings regarding Gender Equality, helping to set the baseline for developing their roadmaps for institutional change.

In this view, the aim of this document is to support the IOs in

1. Analysing their existing institutional GEP, reflecting on the scope and targets, identifying strengths and gaps in relationship to the EC recommended areas, and analysing the 4-l dimensions.
2. Describing the institutional baseline at the beginning of the project in order to assure a reference point for the assessment of the achieved institutional changes at the end of the project.
3. Reflecting and preparing for the next step in the roadmap development.

The document will also be used by the 'model organisation' (Faculty of Education, Department of Food and Nutrition and Sport Science, UGOT) in order to identify the working institutional settings and practices that could serve as inspiration to the SUPPORTER IOs.

The self-assessment is the interphase of the **analytical process** and the **reflective process** of the SUPPORTER project. The analytical process included the [mapping of national and institutional policies \(D2.1\)](#), done by the IOs with the support of UGOT. The reflective process begins with the current self-assessment that will provide a detailed mapping of the institutional arrangements, opportunities and challenges that could then be used to co-create the roadmaps.

The document is divided into two sections:

- [Section 1: GEP analysis](#)
- [Section 2: Institutional mapping](#)

Note: this is an internal document of SUPPORTER project, the data/information/knowledge provided here will not be published neither included in any public deliverable without the prior approval of the partners. However, please avoid providing any personal data, such as names, surnames, email addresses, etc (i.e. anything that let someone be identifiable).

Section 1 – GEP analysis

Building on the mapping done under T2.1, the results of which are presented in [D2.1 “Inclusive gender+ equality policy and practice in sport higher education institutions”](#), and the institutional GEP, please fill in the following information:

Please copy here the link to your institutional GEP:

According to the [Horizon Europe work programme, a GEP](#) should consist of the following elements:

Mandatory process-based elements

These are the minimum process-related requirements to be eligible for EC funding.

Public document

A GEP is a formal document published on the organisation’s website, signed by the top management and actively communicated within your organisation.

- Is your institutional GEP available at your institutional website?
 - Is the full GEP available or only a summary?
 - In which languages is it available?
- Has the GEP been signed by the top management? If yes, by whom (e.g. rector, dean, vice-dean)?
- Only for sports faculties that belong to a University:
 - Does your faculty have a GEP?
 - Does any other faculty have a GEP?

Dedicated resources

A GEP must include a commitment to provide sufficient resources and expertise in gender equality for implementation.

- Is it explicitly mentioned in your GEP the funds that are destined to its implementation?
 - If yes, have these been sufficient so far?

- Is it explicitly mentioned in your GEP who will be in charge of implementing it?
 - If yes, does this people have expertise in gender equality?

Data collection and monitoring

A GEP should be informed by collecting and analysing sex-disaggregated data on personnel (and students, for the relevant organisations). Organisations should report progress annually based on specific indicators.

- Is it described in your GEP how the gender/sex-disaggregated data will be collected and analysed?
 - If yes, does the people in charge of this task have experience and knowledge in gender equality?

- Does the GEP mention how progress will be reported and/or communicated and how often?

- Does the GEP define indicators (qualitative and/or quantitative) to keep track of progress?

Training

A GEP must include awareness-raising and training activities on gender equality for the whole organisation and training on unconscious gender biases for staff and decision-makers.

- Does the GEP define awareness-raising activities?
 - If yes, to whom are these targeted to? (e.g. academic staff, staff in general, students, etc.)

- Does the GEP define training activities?

- If yes, to whom are these targeted to? (e.g. academic staff, staff in general, students, etc.)
- Are some of them tailored to the sports field?

Recommended content-related elements

These are not official requirements but recommended elements to include in the institutional GEPs.

Work–life balance and organisational culture

For more information and examples, please refer to: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/work-life-balance-and-organisational-culture>

- Does your GEP has actions addressing work-life balance and/or organisational culture?
 - If yes, could you please list below these actions?

Gender balance in leadership and decision-making

For more information and examples, please refer to: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/gender-balance-leadership-and-decision-making>

- Does your GEP has actions addressing gender balance in leadership and decision-making?
 - If yes, could you please list below these actions?

Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

For more information and examples, please refer to: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/gender-equality-recruitment-and-career-progression>

- Does your GEP has actions addressing gender equality in recruitment and/or in career progression?
 - If yes, could you please list below these actions?

Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content

For more information and examples, please refer to: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/integration-gender-dimension-research-and-teaching-content>

- Does your GEP has actions addressing the integration of gender dimension into research and/or teaching content?
 - If yes, could you please list below these actions?

Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

For more information and examples, please refer to: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/measures-against-gender-based-violence-including-sexual-harassment>

- Does your GEP have actions against GBV?
 - If yes, could you please list below these actions?

4I-GEP elements

As stated in SUPPORTER's grant agreement, the ultimate goal of the project is to co-create 4I-GEPs that are tailored to sports higher education institutions, explicitly addressing GBV. The 4Is stand for: intersectional, innovative, inclusive and impactful GEPs. According to you, how would you rate these different dimensions in your current GEP:

Dimensions	Rate (please mark with an X)				
	1 (not addressed)	2	3	4	5 (fully addressed)
Intersectional					
Innovative					
Inclusive					
Impactful					
Tailored to sports					
Addressing GBV					

Comments:

Other GEP elements

- Are these elements taken into account in your GEP:

Element	Yes/No	Comment:
Objectives		
Measures/Actions		
Indicators		
Targets		
Timeline		
Responsibilities		

- Does your GEP explicitly connect to other important strategy documents and processes of your organisation? (e.g. Code of conduct, harassment policy, research strategy, etc.)
 - If yes, please mention to which ones.

Section 2 – Institutional mapping

The institutional mapping is structured along 4 areas of intervention:

- Policies, documents & procedures;
- Education & awareness;
- Infrastructure & resources;
- Governance.

Note for the Sport Faculties: within this mapping, please refer to the institutional context (at university level) as well as the faculty context (for the sport faculty in particular).

1 Policies, documents & procedures

Strategy:

- Besides your institutional GEP, is gender equality or inclusion integrated in your institutional academic strategy or in institutional statements? And at faculty level?
- Does your organisation have other gender-related policies?
 - If yes, can you shortly describe them? Is GBV or sexual harassment considered at any of these policies?
- Is your organisation currently developing any other norms, regulations and policies that specifically refer to gender equality or GBV?
 - If yes, can you shortly describe them?

Staff composition and evaluation:

- Is gender equality or gender balance taken into account when hiring academic staff?
- Is the participation in gender equality-related projects, programmes or activities considered as an asset in evaluation schemes (for hiring or evaluating current staff)?
- Can you access gender/sex-disaggregated data of the academic staff and/or students?

- If yes, are other genders considered or only women/men?
- How are the gender statistics for each position? Please fill in the following table with the information available:

Category (e.g. students, academic staff, administrative staff, management, etc)	Women (%)	Men (%)	Other (%), if applicable

- Is the gender/sex-disaggregated data analysed by someone with skills in gender equality?

Management:

- Does your organisation organise presentations on gender equality at management level?
- Does your organisation have any “advocate” or change agent of gender equality at the management level?
- Are researchers/professors being encouraged by management to organise or participate in gender equality activities?
- Do you believe that gender equality a priority in the institutional agenda?

2 Education and awareness

Awareness

- From 0 to 5 how would you score the awareness for gender equality among your academic personnel?
 - Is the existence of gender inequality acknowledged?

- How would you evaluate the awareness of students and staff of the existence and actions described on the GEP?
- How would you evaluate the awareness of students and staff of the procedures to report a case of GBV?
- In the past four years, has there been any gender equality focused event organised?

Capacity building:

- What do you think about the expertise regarding gender equality methodologies of the academic staff (e.g., methodologies on how to engage women in decision-making, deal with data privacy aspects, assure data quality?)
- Does your organisation offer training and workshops on gender equality for researchers, support staff, students, or post-graduates?
 - If yes, could you shortly describe them or add a link (if available), please, or provide a link to the training descriptions if available?

3 Organisational structure & resources

Resources:

- Are there funds dedicated to promoting gender equality at your institution (besides SUPPORTER project)?
 - If yes, which is the origin of these funds? (e.g.: other EC projects, general budget, national projects, etc.)
- Is there any support material on gender equality available? (e.g. guidelines, toolkits, document repositories)

Networks & certifications:

- Do you actively cooperate and/or network with organisations that are active in the gender equality field?
 - If yes, how many approximately?
 - Could you briefly describe them, please (e.g., University alliances, NGOs, Sport academies etc.)?
- Does your organisation have any certification or had won any national or international award on gender equality? (e.g. HRS4R)

Organisational structure:

- Is there an appointed gender equality officer/group among your institution?
- Is there an appointed harassment officer or contact point at your institution?
 - If yes, from which organisational structure this person(s) belongs to?
- Who is in charge of implementing the GEP? Please briefly describe their job positions and roles in the GEP implementation.

4 Governance & change agents

- Are you able to identify “change agents” at your organisation (faculty or university level)?
 - If yes, how many and which is their job position?
 - Have you already been in contact with any of them?
- Is gender analysis included in unit/faculty reports or assessments for internal monitoring?

Other aspects that might be relevant to consider:

Annex 2 – Training Modules content and objectives

Training Module 1: Basic training on key concepts, institutional change, gender equality, gender-based violence and GEPs

Session 1: Key concepts and shared understanding

Content

- What's at stake: Why do we need gender+ equality in research and higher education?
- Key concepts: gender, gender+, intersectionality
- Problems related to gender, gender+ and intersectionality
 - Defining gender equality, gender equality visions and strategies
 - Gender-based violence in the higher education context: prevalence and consequences
- Key concepts: gender-based violence, including sexual harassment
- Exercise/group work

Learning objectives

- Creating awareness of what is at stake, why gender equality and addressing gender-based violence are important
- Building knowledge on gender-based violence (prevalence and consequences) in the European Research Area
- Creating a shared understanding of key concepts, including gender, gender+, intersectionality and gender-based violence.
- Gender-based violence: prevalence and consequences in the European Research Area

Session 2: Institutional change

Content

- European Commission framing of institutional change
- Institutional change: definitions and pathways
- Institutional change, gender equality, and gender-based violence in HEI
- Introduction to gender equality plans
- Institutional gender+ (equality) analysis

Learning objectives

- Creating a baseline and shared understanding of institutional change in higher education institutions
- Identifying routes to institutional change towards gender+ equality
- Identifying the key components of an institutional gender+ (equality) analysis)

Session 3: Gender equality plans

Content

- Recap of institutional change and a gender equality plan as an instrument
- Presentation of the key components/steps of a gender equality plan
- Stakeholder mappings: change agents, core teams, network of allies – presentation and practical exercise
- Key success factors
 - Introduction to supporting gender equality change agents
- The resistance framework: Dealing with resistances and challenges to gender+ equality and gender equality plans

Learning objectives

- Designing a gender equality plan
- Key components of a gender equality plan
- Dealing with resistances and challenges to gender+ equality and gender equality plan implementation
- Supporting gender equality change agents

Training Module 2: Intermediate training on gender equality and inclusive and progressive gender equality plans

Learning objectives

- Creating knowledge on the availability, analysis and assessment of the state-of-play in the institution, including data, and policy and measures.
- Setting up a gender equality plan
- Supporting self-reflection on one's own priority sets and change strategies
- Mutual learning and exchange: Getting inspiration and knowledge from others

Session 1: Analysis and assessment of the state-of-play in the institution: data collection and data analysis; focus on sport higher education institutions – focus data

Content

- The sport higher education environment: key similarities and differences, and challenges, in relation to gender equality, gender-based violence and intersectionality
- The sport higher education environment: prevalence on gender-based violence
- Identifying, collecting, and analysing gender+ segregated data in higher education institutions and research.

Session 2: Analysis and assessment of the state-of-play in the institution: measures, policy and legislation; focus on sport higher education institutions – focus policy and measures

Content

- Identifying and reviewing existing policy and policy measures promoting gender+ equality at the institutional level
- Analysing and identifying gaps in existing policy and policy measures promoting gender+ equality at the institutional level
- Reviewing and assessing policy and policy measures at the national level supporting the institutional gender equality plan

Session 3: Setting up a gender equality plan; focus on sport higher education institutions

Content

- Identification of institutional gender equality plan objectives
- Setting targets and measures to remedy the identified problems. The role of indicators.
- Allocating resources and responsibilities
- Defining timelines

Training Module 3: Advanced training on gender+ equality and 4I-GEPs

Session 1: Implementing a gender equality plan (step 4)

Content:

- Review of key concepts and practical examples, including 4Is
- Implementing the planned activities: identifying step and addressing resistances
- Enlarging the stakeholders' network

Session 2: Monitoring progress and evaluating of a gender equality plan (step 5)

Content:

- Assessment of the implementation process
- Assessing the progress achieved against the aims and objectives identified in the GEP

Session 3: What comes after the gender equality plan (step 6)

Content:

- Sustainability, vulnerability, building momentum lessons learnt
- Development of the next GEP building on experiences, learnings, and achievements
- Ensuring the sustainability of these actions

Annex 3 – Mutual Learning Activities content and objectives

Mutual Learning Workshops

Mutual learning workshop I: Introduction to the Mutual Learning Programme

Content:

- Introduction to the Mutual Learning programme
- Reflection on National and Institutional Frameworks
- Reflection on Training Module I
- Introduction to institutional mapping

Objectives:

- Introduce the Mutual Learning Programme and its individual components
- Provide IOs with the opportunity to discuss and reflect on the national and institutional frameworks as well as on the knowledge acquired through the first training module
- Introduce the institutional mapping exercise (guidance document and template)

Mutual learning workshop II: Gender+ segregated data, state/local policies and regulations

Content:

- Reflection on Training Module II
- Exercise on Gender+ segregated data
- Exercise on state/local policies and regulations
- Using best practices in individual roadmaps

Objectives:

- Reflect on key concepts explored in Training Module II
- Develop further IOs' understanding of gender segregated data
- Assist IOs in identifying best practices and challenges in gender segregated data and state/local policies and regulations
- Reflect on how these practices can be incorporated into individual roadmaps

Mutual learning workshop III: GEP implementation, monitoring and evaluation

Content:

- Reflection on Training Module III
- 4I-GEPs: best practices in GEP implementation, monitoring and evaluation
- Exercises on 4I-GEPs
- Putting 4I-GEP theory into practice

Objectives:

- Reflect on key concepts explored in Training Module III
- Develop further IOs' understanding of 4I-GEPs
- Assist IOs in identifying best practices and challenges in GEP implementation, monitoring and evaluation
- Connect 4I-GEP theory to practice

Mutual Learning Sessions

Mutual learning session I: Introduction to Roadmaps: Co-design

- Introduction to Roadmaps and Co-design: Steps to be taken
- Roadmap template
- Expectations and challenges
- Room for improvement: the case of the Model Institution
- Introduction to Bilateral Meetings among IOs
- Internal stakeholder mapping
- Key issues resulting from the self-assessment exercises
- Clarification of key gender+ equality concepts
- Exercise on Roadmaps

Objectives:

- Facilitate a profound understanding of the co-design process – next step in the project and the related actions and timeline
- Delve into key concepts related to WP4, i.e. roadmap, grounding actions, reflection tool etc.
- Engage IOs in internal stakeholder mapping which is integral for the next step of the co-design
- Present and explain in detail the roadmap template
- Think together and consolidate the learnings from the first training module, the first mutual learning workshop and the institutional mapping completed in T2.3
- Elucidate previously discussed – but seemingly still confusing – ideas/terms to ensure that the development of the institutional roadmaps is based on uniform conceptual grounds (such as gender equality vs. gender balance, 4Is, change agents etc.)

Mutual learning session II: Roadmap Implementation: Challenges and Engagement of Stakeholders

- Learning Diaries
- Challenges in the implementation of Grounding Actions
- Engagement with the local stakeholder network
- Updating the institutional roadmaps

Objectives

- Present and explain the Learning Diaries

- Provide IOs with the opportunity to discuss and reflect on the challenges in the implementation of Grounding Actions
- Explore tools and methods for engaging further with the local stakeholders

Mutual learning session III: Roadmap Implementation: Focus on Sports Education Institutions

- Introduction to gender+ equality in Sports Education Institutions
- Challenges and opportunities for the implementation process
- Examples of Grounding Actions with a specific focus on Sports Education
- Revisiting Grounding Actions

Objectives:

- Introduce gender+ equality in Sports Education Institutions
- Provide examples of Grounding Actions pertaining to gender+ equality in Sports Education
- Provide IOs with the opportunity to discuss and reflect on the challenges in the implementation of Grounding Actions
- Revisit Grounding Actions in relation to gender+ equality in Sports Education Institutions

Mutual learning session IV: Roadmap Implementation: Gender-based Violence

- Introduction to gender-based violence
- Types of gender-based violence
- Gender-based violence and 4I-GEPs: omissions, challenges and implementation
- Revisiting Grounding Actions in relation to gender-based violence

Objectives:

- Develop further IOs' understanding of gender-based violence
- Discuss the different types of gender-based violence
- Consider gender-based violence in relation to 4I-GEPs and reflect on possible omissions
- Provide IOs with the opportunity to discuss and reflect on the challenges in the implementation of Grounding Actions
- Revisit Grounding Actions in relation to gender-based violence

Mutual learning session V: Roadmap Implementation: Sustainability and Long-Term Planning

- What is a sustainable and long-term GEP?
- Sustainable and long-term Grounding Actions
- Examples from other institutions
- Exercises on implementing sustainable and long-term Grounding Actions with a clear focus on Sports Education and gender-based violence

Objectives:

- Present and discuss the concepts of sustainability and long-term planning in relation to GEPs
- Provide examples of sustainable and long-term Grounding Actions with a clear focus on Sports Education and gender-based violence
- Revisit Grounding Actions to ensure sustainability and long-term GEPs

Annex 4 – Learning Diary Templates

**Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with
Intersectional, Innovative, and Inclusive
Gender Equality Plans**

Learning Diary

Document name: <e.g. Learning Diary 1, 2, 3 etc.>

Author: <Add the name of your institution>

Submission date: [DD. MM. YY]

Project acronym:	SUPPORTER
No. of Learning Diary:	<e.g. Learning Diary 1,2,3>
Submission date:	[DD. MM. YY]
Time frame covered by this Learning diary:	[DD. MM. YY – DD. MM. YY]
Person(s) responsible for the diary entry:	
Implementing Organisation's name:	
Monitoring and Mentoring Partner:	<SEERC / ESF / UGOT>
Work Package:	WP3

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General Comments	Error! Bookmark not defined.

Introduction

The SUPPORTER Project aims to assist you in the creation of innovative, inclusive and impactful gender equality plans (4I-GEPs), adjusted to the particularities of sports higher education. To do so, Work Package 3 combines three different schemes. First, the capacity-building scheme, which consists of three training modules which offer a deep and uniform understanding of institutional change, gender+ equality in the sports education context and the development of GEPs. Second, the Mutual Learning scheme, which promotes the meaningful interaction among you as implementing organisations and the consortium as a whole, through the exchange of good practices. And third, the Monitoring and Mentoring scheme, under which the mentoring team will assist each implementing organisation individually, by providing guidance for the co-creation and implementation of the institutional roadmaps.

One of the most important tools to facilitate this mentoring process is the Learning Diary (LD). The learning diary is a record, in the form of a field book, of all the activities and reflections of each implementing organisation within a specific period. During the implementation of institutional roadmaps, each organisation will prepare *five* learning diaries in order to report on the actions planned and to collect insights on the project's activities and outcomes. These are Learning Diaries 2, 3, 4, 6 and 7, and they will be developed with the help of Template 2 found in this document.

To also ensure that the trainings offered under the capacity-building scheme are relevant and essential to you, you are invited to draft two more learning diaries with a different format. These diaries will focus on the understanding of key concepts, the existing needs and your aspirations regarding the upcoming training and mutual learning activities. These are Learning Diaries 1 and 5, and they will be developed with the help of Template 1 found in this document.

The learning diaries are not an evaluation tool, and they will not be shared with anyone outside the consortium. They are rather a self-reflection tool, for internal use only, to help you keep track of what is being done under the project, and to allow the mentoring team to better understand your needs and support you in the implementation of all the activities and grounding actions of your roadmaps.

Please prepare each learning diary using the relevant template and adding the corresponding number in the document title. Each learning diary shall be submitted to the respective WP3 folder on Microsoft SharePoint by the final submission date. Upon submission, you may inform your monitoring team and organise a bilateral mentoring and monitoring meeting with them in order to discuss advancements on the institutional roadmaps and seek guidance with respect to future activities and required actions both during and after the project period. Table 1 depicts the time plan, the area of focus of the learning diary and the respective template to be used for its drafting. Table 2 links each IO to their mentoring contact team.

Table 1

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Month</i>	<i>Final Submission date</i>	<i>Focus</i>	<i>Template</i>
Learning Diary 1	February 2024 (M11)	25/02/2024	Training Module I & II	1
Learning Diary 2	May 2024 (M14)	25/05/2024	Roadmap Implementation	2
Learning Diary 3	September 2024 (M18)	15/09/2024	Roadmap Implementation	2
Learning Diary 4	December 2024 (M21)	15/12/2024	Roadmap Implementation	2
Learning Diary 5	January 2025 (M22)	25/01/2025	Training Module III (4I-GEPs)	1
Learning Diary 6	April 2025 (M25)	25/04/2025	Roadmap Implementation	2
Learning Diary 7	July 2025 (M28)	15/07/2025	Roadmap Implementation	2

Table 2

<i>Implementing Organisation</i>	<i>Month</i>
GSTUPES	ESF (Ildi and Eugenia)
SUPES	
NSA	
UVT	
UNIBL	SEERC (Faye)
UL	
LSU	
CU	SEERC (Zoi Tatsioka)

Template 1: Learning Diary [Insert number] on the capacity-building programme

Learning outcomes from the previous training module

Understanding

Following the first cycle of trainings and mutual learnings, how do you understand and operationalise gender, gender equality, intersectionality, gender-based violence and gender equality in sports in your specific IOs context? For example, numerical versus substantive, gender bias in recruitment, equal pay, inequality grounds, forms of violence, issue of coaching, gendered fields of sport?

Description

Think through and describe how you identified the relevant stakeholders from the mapping (the core group) and how you set it up. For example, did you conduct a new stakeholder mapping and how; did you use an existing gender equality committee, nothing existed before, or something else?

Internal stakeholders' involvement in the training activities

Based on your stakeholder mapping, which stakeholders¹ are included in your core group to in designing the grounding actions to achieve your 4I-GEP?

¹ [D5.1 Dissemination, Engagement and Exploitation Strategy](#) entails the following non-exhaustive list of internal stakeholders: a) IOs' internal institutional network (internal decision-makers, governance, HR, employee representatives/unions, student unions...), and b) IOs' external networks (sports ecosystem, similar academic institutions, various sports organisations, local and national sports organisations networks, students, athletes, general public). The same document non-exhaustively refers to the following potential external stakeholders: SUPPORTER's network at various levels: 'sister' and related projects, RPOs from Eastern Europe and all over Europe, policymakers, RFOs, research communities working in the gender equality field (COPs), and the general public. In the identification of internal stakeholders, you may also use the Internal Stakeholder Mapping you carried out in the framework of the online Mutual Learning Workshop in December, which launched the co-design of your roadmap.

Reflecting on good practices

Reflection on successful experiences / practices

Could you reflect on what worked well in identifying and setting up your core group? For example, do you have any positive experiences regarding intersectionality, diversity and inclusion?

Use of specific tools

Which of the introduced methods/tools for the stakeholder mapping (e.g. the “Different degree of involvement: from core to occasional members –different circles of involvement - and classification according to different level of influence and resistance”) did you find most effective and why? See presentation from the training [here](#).

Reflecting on challenges

Description of challenges and resistances

Did you face any challenges/difficulties in identifying and setting up your core group? For example, regarding intersectionality, inclusion and diversity.

Impact of challenges and resistances

How did these obstacles and challenges affect your setting up of the core group?

Impressions

What could/would you do to prevent or to address similar challenges/resistances?

Training needs/future steps

Description of future activities

Please describe what 4I-GEP elements/aspects (objectives, measures/actions, indicators, targets, timeline, responsibilities) you would like to gain a more advanced understanding on. Take into account the training and mutual learning programme (Deliverable D3.1 - you find it in WP1 - > T1.1 -> 2. SUPPORTER Deliverables -> D3.1) and reflect on what you and your core group need.

General Comments

Additional comments

Is there anything else that you would like to consider/suggest regarding future training activities?

Template 2: Learning Diary [Insert number] on the implementation of the institutional roadmaps

Activities in the reporting period

Description of the activities

Please describe the steps/actions that you have taken during this reporting period in relation to the implementation of your institutional roadmap.

Involvement in the activities

Which internal and external stakeholders² have you involved in order to implement your institutional roadmap?

How did you engage them?

What are the stakeholders' tasks and responsibilities?

² [D5.1 Dissemination, Engagement and Exploitation Strategy](#) entails the following non-exhaustive list of internal stakeholders: a) IOs' internal institutional network (internal decision-makers, governance, HR, employee representatives/unions, student unions...), and b) IOs' external networks (sports ecosystem, similar academic institutions, various sports organisations, local and national sports organisations networks, students, athletes, general public). The same document non-exhaustively refers to the following potential external stakeholders: SUPPORTER's network at various levels: 'sister' and related projects, RPOs from Eastern Europe and all over Europe, policymakers, RFOs, research communities working in the gender equality field (COPs), and the general public.

In the identification of internal stakeholders, you may also use the Internal Stakeholder Mapping you carried out in the framework of the online Mutual Learning Workshop in December, which launched the co-design of your roadmap.

Use of specific tools

Could you elaborate on the methods you employed to organise and carry out your actions?
(e.g. design of questionnaires/interview guides, dissemination methods or techniques to recruit participants etc.)

Table 3: Schematic representation of implemented activities

Type of activity	Date	Location	Involved stakeholders	Main objective	Employed tools

Best practices

Description of Successful Experiences / Accomplishments

Could you describe any good practices/ successful experiences within the reporting period?

Note: This could be in reference to both the implementation of the institutional roadmap and the other activities of the SUPPORTER project (e.g. mutual learning programme).

2. Impressions

Have these activities you carried out during this reporting period satisfied the success criteria you have established for your institutional roadmap?

Have you been able to reach the targeted stakeholder groups?

Challenges

Description of Challenges and Obstacles

Did you face any challenges/difficulties in achieving the reporting period's goals? (e.g. difficulty in organising activities/recruiting participants, difficulty in obtaining necessary resources etc.)

How did you tackle these obstacles and challenges?

Note: This could be in reference to both the implementation of the institutional roadmap and the other activities of the SUPPORTER project (e.g. mutual learning programme).

Impact of Challenges and Obstacles

How did these obstacles and challenges affect the results of your initiative or action?

Impressions

Why do you think the specific obstacles emerged?

What kind of actions could be attempted in the future to not only tackle obstacles, but to prevent them altogether?

Future steps

Description of Future Activities

Please briefly describe your plans for the upcoming reporting period (events, meetings, other types of activities).

Would you need any help (discussions/suggestions) from other partners in this project to carry out your planned activities?

General Comments

Additional comments

Is there anything else that you would like to report regarding your activities during this reporting period?

